

ISic0820

Fragment of a base or altar, which mentions an aedes

Language

Latin

Type

dedication / building

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

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Autopsy

2015.07.03

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Adranon

Place of origin (modern)

Adrano

Provenance

Found during construction work for an irrigation cistern in 1959, within the so-called Dionysian walls, in contrada Mola,

Coordinates

37.6593098, 14.8251446

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Adrano, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Adrano, inventory 11701

Physical Description

An irregular fragment of grey limestone (perhaps from the south bank of the Simeto river), broken on all sides, with only parts of the front and rear faces preserved. The rear presents a regular surface, picked rather than smooth. The front has the remains of a recessed panel, with part of the left margin preserved proud of the surface. The surface of the panel is lightly curved, in convex fashion along the horizontal plane, suggesting a cylindrical shape for the original block/monument from which the fragment derives.

Dimensions

Height 27 cm

Width 19 cm

Depth 21 cm

Layout

The inscribed panel is 0.115 m high at the left margin and has a maximum preserved height of 0.14 m, reducing to c. 0.095 m on the right margin; the maximum preserved width of the panel is 0.12 m. The inscription, of which traces of 6 lines are visible, is set out in the recessed panel. Part of the left margin of the text is preserved, but the full extent of the text is unknown, probably continuing above, right and below.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are incised with a deep V-cut, and are of regular and squarish form, with small serifs. There is a single instance of ligature at the start of line 2. An unusual double interpunct is employed in line 4 (double interpuncts are rare in Latin epigraphy; although no interpunct is visible between

the S and P of line 4,
there is otherwise no point in the rest of the surviving text
where one would expect
an interpunct to be deployed, so it is difficult to speculate
as to whether the
double interpunct is used for a particular reason at this
point in the text). Lines
4 and 5 both employ a superscript letter R to create what
appears to be an
unparalleled abbreviation both in form and letters: the
superscript R on line 4
extends up into line 3; the superscript R on line 5 extends
up to the base of line 4.

Letter heights:

Line 1: incomplete mm

Line 2: 21 mm

Line 3: 23-25 mm

Line 4: 25 mm

Line 5: 26 mm

Line 6: incomplete mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 10 mm

Interlineation line 2 to 3: 7-9 mm

Interlineation line 3 to 4: 13 mm

Interlineation line 4 to 5: 8 mm

Interlineation line 5 to 6: 10 mm

Text

1. a [---]

2. âede ṁ [---]

3. care [---]

4. s (ua) p (ecunia) : d ṛ : [---]

5. (vac.2)d r [---]

6. [..] + [---]

Apparatus

Text of Prag, based on autopsy

Manganaro (1961) 131 asserted that "nella linea 3 la quarta lettera é sicuramente i,

mentre la lett. successiva poteva essere n, in margine alla quale

si sia verificata la

rottura della pietra", and proposed the name Cari[nus]. The fourth letter is quite clearly an E: the curvature and erosion of the stone mean that the upper and middle bars of the E are very faint, but the lower bar is absolutely clear. The traces which Manganaro suggested were compatible with N at the end of the same line appear rather to belong to a letter R, in a superscript position following the D in line 4, as is more clearly visible at the end of line 5.

Manganaro did not comment on the traces of one or more letters visible below line 5. The

remaining traces are most readily compatible with M or N.

Translation

Commentary

The text makes reference to an aedes ('temple', or 'shrine'), and to something being done at the personal expense (*sua pecunia*) of the individual responsible for the text or being honoured in the text. These two elements suggest that the inscription referred to an act of building / euergetism related to the construction, repair, or decoration of the aedes. Given the curving form of the fragment, the suggestion by MANGANARO (1961, p.131) that this might be part of a cylindrical altar is appealing, although part of a statue base or other monument is no less plausible. The preserved section of the rear face suggests that this was either a relief monument, or a hollow cylindrical one.

The rarity of words beginning care- suggests that line 3 begins with the continuation of a word such as *aedificare* from the previous line. There is no obvious parallel for the form DR. Given its position in the text, seemingly near the end, and separated by the unusual double interpunct, it is reasonable to treat it as an unusual form of abbreviation of the very frequent D(ecreto) D(ecurionum), i.e. D(ec)r(eto) D(ecu)r(ionum) (so already MANGANARO 1961, p. 131). There is no reason to think that the letters were added later (as was suggested by MANGANARO who did not note the second example at the end of line 4), since this is already an atypical form of abbreviation, and there is nothing about the engraving to suggest the letters are by a different hand.

If the letters DR DR are expanded as *decreto decurionum*, then this text may attest to the status of Hadranum in the imperial period as being that of a Latin municipium, but no certainty is possible (for the problems of municipal status in imperial period Sicily, see (inter alia), D. Vera, "Augusto, Plinio il Vecchio e la

Sicilia in età imperiale. A proposito di recenti scoperte epigrafiche e archeologiche ad Agrigento", *Kokalos* 42 (1996), 31-58 and J. R. W. Prag, "Sicilia Romana tributim discripta", in M. Silvestrini (ed.), *Le tribu romane. Atti della XVIe rencontre sur l'épigraphie* (Bari 8-10 ottobre 2009) (Bari 2010), 305-311.

This is the only surviving inscription in Latin from the ancient site of Adranum.

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Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 1961. *Iscrizioni di Adrano. PdP.* 16: 126-135. At 130-132 fig.2

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Photo J. Prag